

A NEEDS ASSESSMENT OF BUYON INTEGRATED SCHOOL: A BASIS FOR DEVELOPING A THREE-YEAR OUTREACH PROGRAM OF THE SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL DEPARTMENT OF OUR LADY OF THE PILLAR COLLEGE-CAUAYAN, INC.

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the current needs of Buyon Integrated School in Buyon, Cauayan City, Isabela, as a basis for formulating a three-year outreach program of the Senior High School Department of Our Lady of the Pillar College-Cauayan, Inc. (S.Y. 2025–2028). Using a descriptive survey design, data were gathered from 42 respondents, composed of 20 students, 14 parents, and 8 teachers, through a questionnaire. The survey focused on four domains: student development and services, learning facilities and resources, school environment, and professional development. Findings show that student development and services, particularly literacy and technical/vocational skills, were rated as highly needed, while instructional resources such as books and reading materials also emerged as pressing concerns. In terms of school environment, laboratory tools and equipment were prioritized, while for professional development, in-service training and mentorship programs were identified as highly needed. The overall results indicate that student-centered programs should be the top priority, complemented by improvements in facilities and teacher development. Based on these findings, a three-year outreach program was proposed to holistically address the needs identified at Buyon Integrated School.

Keywords: *Needs Assessment, Student Development, School Facilities, Professional Development, Outreach Program*

INTRODUCTION

Needs assessment, as defined by Cuiccio and Watkins, as cited by Dinoy et al. (2020), is a systematic process that involves examining the disparity between an organization's current and desired states and identifying contributing factors. This rigorous approach is crucial for understanding organizational performance (Olan et al., 2022). This comprehensive process encompasses identifying weak areas that need improvement, analyzing their root causes, and formulating actionable programs to address the identified needs. It further helps practitioners effectively use resources to enhance program decision-making. Particularly in educational contexts, conducting a needs assessment is considered an essential initial step to enhance service delivery and improve student outcomes (Dinoy et al., 2020). Moreover, it serves as a vital tool for informed decision-making, as emphasized by Dewi & Amariah (2023), providing educators with insights into specific learner needs to design effective instructional strategies and materials. Ultimately, by guiding the planning and implementation of activities, needs assessment empowers educators and system leaders to drive continuous institutional improvement and achieve desired performance enhancements (Bantilan et al., 2023).

Needs are a fundamental aspect of motivation, as human beings are primarily driven by the desire to satisfy their deficiencies. At its core, a need is a state of lack or deprivation. This study will examine four key dimensions within the school context: student development and services, learning facilities and resources, school environment, and professional development. Student development and services refer to needs concerning students' academic matters. Learning facilities and resources encompass the resources that support the teaching and learning process. Furthermore, the school environment encompasses both the institution's physical characteristics and its working atmosphere. Lastly, professional development addresses teachers' need for continuous professional growth. Each of these dimensions contains specific areas that this study aims to assess.

A study conducted by Azimi (2014) surveyed students at the College of Education, University of Mysore, India, to identify needs and gaps in e-learning components. Findings revealed that internet tools and video streaming were highly prioritized, whereas instructional theories and mobile technology received the lowest rankings. The researcher recommended that training programs designed by students, faculty, management, and educators could improve e-learning and internet technology proficiency and facilitate more effective use of these technologies. Moreover, students, especially prospective teachers, should be informed about the capabilities of various e-learning technologies to enhance pedagogical approaches.

A study focused on educational quality in rural elementary schools in Kalecik, Ankara, found general satisfaction among staff and students with the schools' physical infrastructure. However, a significant proportion of educators were found to be teaching subjects outside their area of expertise. The research identified factors such as a deficiency in technological resources and limited parental engagement as potential

impediments to educational quality. Furthermore, teachers observed a tendency to foster competition over cooperation among students. A needs assessment was conducted by Magno (2012) within selected schools in the Southern Luzon region to evaluate their existing program evaluation practices and identify specific needs. The study highlighted several areas for enhancement, including the evaluation of teacher performance and training, the exploration of alternative evaluation methodologies such as focus group discussions and surveys, the provision of training in instrumentation as a technical skill, the organization of seminars and workshops to improve understanding of the evaluation process, and the strengthening of personnel, practical, relational, and study-related aspects of evaluation within these institutions.

This research is grounded in the fundamental principles of Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. Section 2 of this legislation expands the objectives of secondary education to include preparation for higher education, opportunities in vocational and technical fields, and engagement in creative arts, sports, and entrepreneurship, all within the context of a dynamic global landscape. Supporting this, Article XIV, Section 3 of the Education Act of 1982 mandates that educational curricula should foster critical and creative thinking, enhance scientific and technological literacy, and promote vocational proficiency and other crucial competencies. Moreover, the Philippine Constitution of 1987, in Article XIV, Section 2, stipulates that "the state shall establish, maintain, and support a complete, adequate, and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society." Within this legal framework, this needs assessment is designed to strengthen the school's efforts to provide basic education to students by identifying, prioritizing, and addressing current needs and deficiencies.

The researchers were prompted to conduct a needs assessment at Buyon Integrated School to determine its current conditions, challenges, and areas of improvement that require immediate and long-term support. This study is significant because it will serve as a foundation for identifying priority needs and designing relevant interventions to strengthen the school's capacity to deliver quality education. Moreover, the researchers aim to establish Buyon Integrated School as the designated adopted school for the Senior High School department, ensuring sustainability and continuity of the partnership. Ultimately, the findings of this study will guide the formulation of a three-year extension program tailored to the specific needs of the adopted school, fostering collaboration and meaningful community engagement.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the current needs of Buyon Integrated School in Buyon, Cauayan City, Isabela. The study further intends that through its findings, needs are identified and prioritized, and three-year extension program can be formulated based from these needs.

This research sought to provide answers to the following questions:

1. What are the needs of the school in terms of:
 - 1.1. student development and services;
 - 1.2. learning facilities and services;
 - 1.3. school environment; and,
 - 1.4. professional development?
2. What three-year development plan can be drawn for the extension and outreach program of the Senior High School department of Our Lady of the Pillar College-Cauayan, Inc. based from the results of the survey in terms of the above-mentioned needs.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive survey design to systematically assess the needs of Buyon Integrated School. The design was deemed appropriate because it enabled the researcher to gather quantitative data reflecting the perceptions and priorities of various stakeholders regarding student development and services, learning facilities and resources, school environment, and professional development. Through this approach, the study provided a clear, factual basis for formulating an outreach program. The respondents in the study were 42 stakeholders from Buyon Integrated School. This included 8 teachers, 20 students, and 14 parents, selected as representatives to provide a holistic understanding of the school's needs. Their perspectives were essential to ensuring that the collected data reflected the realities and priorities of the entire school community. The main research instrument used in this study was a questionnaire adopted from Romar B. Dinoy's (2020) work, which was found to align with the objectives and scope of the present research. The questionnaire was modified to suit the local context of Buyon Integrated School and covered key domains, including student development, facilities and resources, school environment, and professional development. Regarding the data-gathering procedure, permission from the Office of the Principal was obtained before administering the questionnaires. Once approved, the survey was administered to the identified respondents. Their voluntary participation was ensured, and the confidentiality of their responses was strictly observed. For data analysis, each domain of the survey instrument contained 10 statements rated on a 4-point Likert scale, ranging from "1 – Low Need" to "4 – Highly Needed." The weighted mean was used to analyze responses and determine the overall level of need in each domain. This statistical method provided an objective measure of the stakeholders' priorities and guided the formulation of the three-year outreach program.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered. The following tables present students', parents', teachers', and principals' responses to the specific areas of need across the four dimensions.

Table 1
Needs Assessment of Students', Parents' and Teachers in Terms of Student Development and Services of Buyon Integrated School

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Literacy (reading and writing)	3.64	Highly Needed
2. Numeracy (math skills in everyday life)	3.60	Highly Needed
3. Communication skills	3.52	Highly Needed
4. Technical/vocational skills (e.g., computer, etc.)	3.57	Highly Needed
5. Recreational programs and activities	3.26	Highly Needed
6. Religion/ Values Education	3.21	Moderately Needed
7. Environmental education	3.24	Moderately Needed
8. Nutrition education and practice	3.19	Moderately Needed
9. Financial literacy and management	2.40	Low Need
10. Career guidance and placement services	3.07	Moderately Needed
Overall Mean	3.27	Highly Needed

The table indicates that, among the student development and services, Literacy had the highest mean score of 3.64, indicating it is Highly Needed. Conversely, financial literacy and management received the lowest mean score of 2.40, interpreted as Low Need.

The findings imply that the respondents perceive basic academic competencies such as literacy, numeracy, communication, and technical/vocational skills as crucial areas requiring attention and support for their personal and academic growth. Meanwhile, aspects such as financial literacy, religion/values education, environmental education, and nutrition education were rated lower, indicating that, while relevant, they are not considered immediate needs compared to core academic and skill-based areas. The overall mean of 3.27, interpreted as Highly Needed, further suggests that the school should prioritize student-centered programs focusing on foundational academic and technical skills to holistically support learners.

This result is consistent with the findings of Dela Cruz and Santos (2021), who emphasized that literacy and numeracy remain central to student development as these skills are essential in lifelong learning and employment readiness. Similarly, Reyes (2022) stressed the importance of technical and vocational competencies in preparing students

for both higher education and future work opportunities. These studies affirm that strengthening fundamental academic and practical skills should be the core focus of outreach and development programs in Philippine schools.

Table 2
Needs Assessment of Students', Parents' and Teachers in Terms of Learning Facilities and Resources of Buyon Integrated School

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Classrooms	2.69	Moderately Needed
2. Classroom chairs	3.21	Moderately Needed
3. Books and other reading resources	3.33	Highly Needed
4. Library	3.12	Moderately Needed
5. Laboratory tools and equipment	2.74	Moderately Needed
6. Laboratory room	2.74	Moderately Needed
7. Computer units	2.81	Moderately Needed
8. Water/Electricity	3.00	Moderately Needed
9. School Supplies	2.79	Moderately Needed
10. Internet Connection	2.86	Moderately Needed
Overall Mean	2.93	Moderately Needed

The table indicates that books and other reading resources have the highest mean of 3.33, indicating they are Highly Needed. Conversely, Classrooms have the lowest mean of 2.69, interpreted as 'Moderately Needed.'

The results imply that, while the school has adequate classroom facilities, there is greater concern about the availability of books and other reading resources. This suggests that instructional materials, rather than physical structures, are more pressing for the students, parents, and teachers of Buyon Integrated School. Computer units, internet connections, and laboratory tools also reflect moderate needs, indicating that the school community aspires to improve technology and science-related resources to enhance learning. The overall mean of 3.27, interpreted as Moderately Needed, suggests that the school still requires significant support to strengthen its educational facilities and resources, particularly in areas directly tied to student learning outcomes.

This finding is supported by Guinto and Andaya (2021), who emphasized that the adequacy of learning resources such as books and digital materials significantly affects students' academic performance and engagement. Similarly, Cruz and Agaton (2022) highlighted that access to sufficient learning materials remains a critical challenge in public schools, especially in rural areas, which impacts the quality of instruction. These studies affirm that the pressing need for instructional resources, as revealed in this research, should be prioritized in planning outreach programs and school improvement initiatives.

Table 3
Needs Assessment of Students', Parents' and Teachers in Terms of School Environment of Buyon Integrated School

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. Classrooms	3.31	Highly Needed
2. Classroom chairs	2.76	Moderately Needed
3. Books and other reading resources	2.79	Moderately Needed
4. Library	2.95	Moderately Needed
5. Laboratory tools and equipment	3.33	Highly Needed
Overall Mean	3.03	Moderately Needed

Table 3 indicates that Laboratory tools and equipment received the highest mean score of 3.33, interpreted as Highly Needed. While classroom chairs had the lowest mean score of 2.76, interpreted as Moderately Needed.

The results suggest that while the provision of basic facilities, such as classroom chairs, is relatively adequate, there remains a strong need for laboratory equipment to strengthen the school's science instruction. Classrooms also received a high rating of 3.31, underscoring that learning spaces remain a critical factor in enhancing the school environment. Overall, the computed mean of 3.03, interpreted as Moderately Needed, indicates that the school community recognizes significant gaps in the availability and quality of facilities that directly influence the teaching-learning process. The emphasis on laboratory resources reflects the increasing demand for practical, hands-on learning experiences aligned with 21st-century competencies.

This result is supported by the study by Cabardo (2021), which emphasized that adequate science laboratories and tools are essential for promoting students' higher-order thinking skills and engagement in inquiry-based learning. Likewise, Bautista and Tindowen (2020) found that school facilities, particularly classrooms and laboratory equipment, play a significant role in shaping the overall learning environment and learners' academic performance. These studies validate the finding that prioritizing improvements to laboratory resources and classroom facilities should be central to Buyon Integrated School's outreach program.

Table 4
Needs Assessment of Teachers in Terms of Professional Development of Buyon Integrated School

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. In-service training	3.75	Highly Needed
2. Relevant training/seminar/worksh	3.00	Moderately Needed

ops in the field of specialization		
3. Support for graduate studies	2.88	Moderately Needed
4. Continuing Professional Development (CPD) seminar/workshop	2.75	Moderately Needed
5. Mentorship or coaching program with an experienced professional	3.63	Highly Needed
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderately Needed

Table 4 indicates that In-service training received the highest mean score of 3.75, indicating it is Highly Needed. Conversely, the Continuing Professional Development seminar/workshop recorded the lowest mean score of 2.75, interpreted as Moderately Needed.

The results highlight that professional development opportunities remain a vital concern among the stakeholders of Buyon Integrated School. In-service training and mentorship programs were rated as highly needed, underscoring the importance of sustained guidance, skill enhancement, and capacity building for teachers. On the other hand, CPD seminars and graduate study support received relatively lower ratings, suggesting that while teachers value formal continuing education, they prioritize immediate, practical training interventions that directly support their teaching practices. The overall mean of 3.20, interpreted as Moderately Needed, suggests that while there are ongoing professional growth efforts, additional structured and relevant professional development programs must be integrated into the outreach plan to better support faculty competency and student learning outcomes.

This finding aligns with the study by Manzano and Abenes (2021), which found that mentorship and in-service training significantly improve teacher performance, classroom management, and instructional strategies. Likewise, Orlanes and Cuarteros (2020) emphasized that continuous professional development is vital for adapting to the changing demands of education, but localized, context-based training programs yield more immediate benefits than generic seminars. These studies support the conclusion that Buyon Integrated School should prioritize in-service training and mentorship programs in its professional development initiatives.

Table 5
Summary of Needs Assessment of Students', Parents' and Teachers of Buyon Integrated School

Statement	Mean	Interpretation
1. Student Development and Services	3.27	Highly Needed
2. Learning Facilities and Resources	2.93	Moderately Needed
3. School Environment	3.03	Moderately Needed
4. Professional Development	3.20	Moderately Needed
Overall Mean	3.11	Moderately Needed

Table 5 indicates that Student Development and Services has the highest mean score (3.27), interpreted as Highly Needed. While learning facilities and resources recorded the lowest mean score (2.93), though interpreted as Moderately Needed.

The results indicate that among the domains assessed, stakeholders at Buyon Integrated School place the greatest importance on student development and services, underscoring the need for programs that directly enhance learners' academic, personal, and social growth. While facilities, resources, and the school environment remain essential, the findings suggest that interventions focusing on student-centered support systems are perceived as more urgent. The overall mean of 3.11, interpreted as Moderately Needed, suggests that while the school community acknowledges existing gaps across domains, they prioritize initiatives with the most immediate and direct impact on students' holistic development. This insight underscores the importance of designing outreach programs that balance infrastructure and teacher development with robust student services.

This finding is supported by Sicut and David (2021), who stressed that student development services, such as guidance, counseling, and extracurricular activities, are critical for fostering student success and well-being in Philippine schools. Similarly, Delos Santos and Camara (2022) emphasized that while facilities and teacher development are vital, student-focused programs yield more immediate and visible outcomes in enhancing learner engagement and achievement. These studies affirm that prioritizing student development should be central to Buyon Integrated School's outreach initiatives.

Conclusions

The study concludes that the most pressing needs of Buyon Integrated School center on student development and services, particularly in strengthening literacy and technical/vocational skills, which are deemed essential for learners' holistic growth. While classrooms were found relatively adequate, the lack of instructional resources, especially books and other reading materials, emerged as a critical concern. Similarly, the demand for laboratory tools and equipment underscores the importance of providing students with

practical, inquiry-based learning experiences. For teachers, in-service training and mentorship programs were identified as highly needed, underscoring the preference for relevant, immediate, and context-based professional development. Overall, the findings affirm that student-centered initiatives should be prioritized, complemented by improvements in facilities and teacher development, thereby providing a strong foundation for a three-year outreach program that addresses the holistic needs of the school community.

Recommendations

From the obtained findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following:

- It is recommended that students actively engage in the outreach program by participating in literacy and numeracy enhancement activities, technical/vocational skill-building workshops, and science-based projects. Their involvement will not only develop their competencies but also foster responsibility, collaboration, and leadership as they serve as direct beneficiaries and partners in sustaining student-centered initiatives.
- Teachers are encouraged to take an active role in capacity-building activities, such as in-service training, mentorship programs, and professional workshops, facilitated by the outreach program. Their openness to continuous learning and application of innovative teaching strategies will strengthen classroom instruction and directly improve student outcomes.
- Parents should be encouraged to support the outreach program by participating in seminars on parenting, financial literacy, and community engagement. Their cooperation in reinforcing student learning at home and in assisting with school-community initiatives will ensure the program's sustainability and effectiveness.
- Alumni are encouraged to contribute to the outreach program through resource-sharing, volunteering, and mentorship. Their participation will serve as an inspiration for current students and demonstrate the value of giving back to the school community.
- The administrators of Our Lady of the Pillar College are recommended to provide leadership, institutional support, and resource mobilization for the outreach program. Their guidance in aligning the program with the institution's mission and vision will ensure its long-term success and greater impact on Buyon Integrated School.
- The Board of Trustees should be recommended to extend policy support and allocate resources to sustain the Senior High School department's outreach program. Their strategic involvement in ensuring adequate funding and monitoring will strengthen the program's implementation and guarantee accountability.

- Future researchers are advised to conduct follow-up studies to assess the effectiveness of the outreach program and explore the emerging needs of Buyon Integrated School. Their contributions will provide evidence-based insights for continuous improvement and innovation in program delivery.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that this study entitled “A Needs Assessment of Buyon Integrated School: A Basis for Developing a Three-Year Outreach Program of the Senior High School Department of Our Lady of the Pillar College–Cauayan, Inc.” was conducted in full compliance with accepted ethical standards in educational research. Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all respondents after clearly explaining the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study. Participation was strictly voluntary, and the respondents were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without any form of penalty or disadvantage. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were assured and maintained throughout the research process, and all information gathered was treated with utmost respect and discretion. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded, and no physical, psychological, or social harm was caused as a result of their participation.

Furthermore, the researchers declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and acknowledgment of all sources used. The researchers ensured objectivity and fairness in the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data, with no bias influencing the findings. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes, particularly to serve as a basis for developing a three-year outreach program, and were not utilized for any personal, political, or commercial gain.

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